

Acknowledgement

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Gravimetric Determination of Selenium with Phenylhydrazine

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LITERATURE provides a number of reagent¹⁻⁵ for the gravimetric determination of selenium. In most of the procedures recommended, selenium is precipitated as its red variety and must be dried cautiously for 4-6 hr before final weighing. Hydroxylamine method is more suitable for selenium but is still not attractive because of the long time needed for digestion. Hovorka⁶ employed hydrazine hydrate in perchloric and hydrochloric acids and reports that the determination of selenium in perchloric acid was unsatisfactory. However, Ooba and Uneo⁷ studied this reaction in perchloric acid for determining selenium in chalcogenide materials, prescribed a minimum of 4 hr digestion at boiling water bath temperature. This paper describes an accurate and relatively rapid gravimetric method for selenium.

Phenylhydrazine has been used very largely as a reagent for the characterisation of carbohydrates. The use of this reagent for the analytical determination of metals has been very limited. It has been

applied for the determination of micro amounts of selenium colorimetrically⁸. Using this the reduction of selenious acid into elementary selenium is accomplished in both tartaric and hydrochloric acid solutions in about 30 min.

Unlike the existing methods the procedure now proposed is rapid and can be completed in about 2 hr.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical purity.

Selenium Solution: A standard solution was prepared by dissolving 1.6329 g of selenious acid (BDH AnalaR 2 grade) in one litre of double distilled water. The amount of selenium was determined using hydroxylamine hydrochloride⁹.

Reagent Solution: 10 ml of phenylhydrazine was dissolved in 100 ml of rectified spirit.

Recommended Procedure: An aliquot of selenium solution (containing 9.90-99.00 mg of C) was transferred to a 400 ml beaker. To this, tartaric acid (20 g) and appropriate amount of reagent solution (1 ml=20 mg Se) were added. The solution was brought to a final volume of 200 ml with distilled water. The beaker was placed on a boiling water bath and heated for 30 min till the black elemental selenium separated. It was then filtered through a G-4 sintered glass crucible, washed free from excess phenylhydrazine with alcohol and dried at 120° to constant weight. The results are listed in Table 1.

TABLE—1a. DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM
Tartaric Acid 20 g; Reagent solution, 5 ml.

Amount of Selenium taken mg	Amount of Selenium found mg	Recovery %
99.00	98.90	99.9
49.50	49.40	99.8
49.50	49.45	99.9
24.75	24.70	99.8
9.90	9.88	99.8

TABLE—1b. DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM IN HYDROCHLORIC ACID (2.0 N)

Amount of Selenium taken mg	Amount of Selenium found mg	Recovery %
10.54	10.50	99.8
21.08	21.14	100.2
31.62	31.58	99.9
42.16	42.16	100.0
52.70	52.64	99.9
63.24	63.18	99.9
84.32	84.12	99.8
115.94	115.94	100.0
126.48	126.28	99.8
147.56	147.68	100.1

Results and Discussion

In order to optimise reaction conditions the influence of tartaric acid, reagent concentration and time required for complete precipitation have been investigated.

Effect of Tartaric Acid and Reagent: Both tartaric acid and reagent concentration influence the rapid recovery of selenium (Table 2). Lower

TABLE-2 EFFECT OF TARTARIC ACID AND REAGENT CONCENTRATION ON SELENIUM DETERMINATION.

Se taken	Tartaric acid added.	Phenylhydrazine added	Digestion time	Se found	Recovery
mg	g	ml	hr	mg	%
49.50	2.0	0.15	3.0	49.30	99.6
49.50	2.0	0.50	3.0	49.40	99.8
24.75	2.0	1.00	3.0	24.75	99.8
24.75	2.0	2.00	3.0	24.68	99.8
9.90	2.0	5.00	3.0	9.89	99.9
49.50	5.00	0.15	3.00	49.40	99.8
99.00	10.00	0.15	3.00	98.90	99.9
24.75	20.00	0.15	3.00	24.70	99.9
24.75	30.00	0.15	3.00	24.70	99.9
49.50	5.00	0.15	0.5	35.05	70.8
24.75	10.00	0.30	0.5	22.10	89.3
24.75	20.00	0.50	0.5	24.70	99.9
9.90	30.00	0.50	0.5	9.86	99.6

acid concentrations prolonged the reaction time too long for practical purposes. Higher concentrations of tartaric acid were chosen in preference to lower acidities because the reduction of selenium occurred more readily at higher acidities and hydrolysable metals were easily kept in solution. The optimum conditions to achieve the rapid recoveries of the metal are 5 to 15% tartaric acid and 0.5 to 1 ml reagent in a final volume of 200 ml. To ensure rapid recoveries of the metal an excess of reagent (0.5-1 ml) is recommended. A large excess of the reagent upto 5 ml however has no adverse effect.

Time: The minimum digestion time required for the quantitative precipitation to be established by varying the amounts of tartaric acid and phenylhydrazine (Table 2). The selenium completely separated after a brief digestion period of 30 min with 10% tartaric acid and 5 ml reagent solution saving time with no sacrifice of accuracy (Table 1). At lower concentrations of both, the reaction needed 3 hr for completion and the precipitate must be allowed to stand preferably overnight.

Diverse Ions: The method permits the determination of selenium in the presence of appreciable amounts of iron, cobalt, cadmium, manganese, nickel, chloride, sulphate and nitrate. Copper, tellurium, chromium and thorium, however, seriously interfere.

Use of Hydrochloric Acid: The reduction to elemental selenium is also accomplished in hydrochloric acid media at boiling water bath temperature. The reaction is complete in 1.0-6.0 N hydrochloric acid, (approximately 10 to 60% by volume). 40 ml of the acid in the total volume of 200 ml was used. The effect of acidity and the time required for complete precipitation are shown in Table 1. The experiments were made by taking varying amounts of selenium as selenious acid adding from 20-60 ml of hydrochloric acid and 5 ml of the reagent. Selenium was determined by the same procedure. In every case the recovery of selenium was quantitative. The precipitation of selenium as its black variety is accomplished in about 30 min. Hydrochloric acid is thus a convenient alternative to tartaric acid.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Oxalic Acid by Ceric Sulphate in Acidic Medium

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CERIC sulphate is one of the strongest oxidising agents with an oxidation potential of 1.43 ± 0.05 Volts in 1-8N sulphuric acid¹. The common valencies of cerium in ceric salts are 3 and 4, in which the probable unhybridised electronic configuration² are $5s^2 5p^6 4d^{10} 4f^1$ and $5s^2 5p^6 4d^{10}$ respectively. The kinetic behaviour of the oxidation